

DETERMINATION OF DENTAL DISEASES AMONG INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION WORKERS

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Summary,

Emphasizing the expansion of light industry enterprises over the years of independence, the implementation of fundamental reforms in the industry, the increase in employment at these enterprises, it is important to protect the health of workers in this industry. Expansion of silkworm production, especially in developed countries, including automation of technological processes and information technology at industrial production enterprises. Their use minimizes direct contact between the processors and the chemicals used in the process, but their impact remains the same. It is also worth noting the unfavorable working conditions in the production process

Key words: light industry enterprises, dental examinations, oral mucosa, symptoms, somatic diseases

Relevance of the topic . The increase in the economic potential of our country, the influx of large amounts of investment, and the establishment and operation of many enterprises, including chemical industry enterprises. Scientific and technical development requires the introduction of various chemical compounds in order to increase the quantity, quality, and variety of the produced products, and to reduce their cost. This situation also applies to industrial enterprises.

The goal. The purpose of this study is to analyze the dental diseases and dental treatment of workers of industrial enterprises living in ecologically unfavorable conditions in the city of Shavot , to identify dental diseases among the workers of the enterprise, to determine the negative impact on the oral cavity, and to develop an assessment of their condition.

Material and methods

In order to carry out scientific research, the health and dental status of workers operating in the industrial enterprise " Textile Finance X orazm " LLC, located in the city of Shavot, was studied and evaluated

350 workers working in this enterprise were involved in research, they are of working age (25-52 years old), they were formed as the main group.

In order to compare the obtained results, local residents living in the neighborhoods around this enterprise formed a control group. 100 residents aged 25-52, who do not work at the industrial enterprise "T extile Finance X orazm " LLC, were recruited into this control group. In both groups, there were more women than men - the number of employees of the industrial enterprise "T extile Finance X orazm " LLC (n=350) 200 were women (58.0±0.9%) and 150 were men (41.4±1.4%). It was 1:1.33 in the community living around the enterprise and 1:1.32 in the control group. It can be seen that the gender difference is the same, which indicates that the study groups are representative of each other.

Conclusions.

It was found that among the workers working in the industrial enterprise "T extile Finance X orazm" LLC, the incidence of the main symptoms of dental diseases is higher than in the population living in the area where the enterprise is located, but not working in the enterprise. 8 out of 9 indicators were found to be 1.5-7.6 times more frequent in workers. Symptoms that differ significantly and require attention in planning preventive measures include increased tooth sensitivity due to food and sweets (7.6 and 6.1 times), bleeding gums (6.2 times), discomfort in the oral cavity (7.4 times).

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